

Evolving co-classifications – measuring technology maturity over time with patents

Melanie Martini¹ and Marcus John²

¹*melanie.martini@int.fraunhofer.de*, ²*marcus.john@int.fraunhofer.de*

Fraunhofer Institute for Technological Trend Analysis INT, Appelsgarten 2, 53879 Euskirchen, (Germany)

Abstract

The IPC and CPC are often used for patent analysis in technology foresight, for example to span a technology field. One important indicator is the co-classification. However, so far, the evolution of the co-classification over the years has been neglected in the research. In this work of progress, we argue, that the temporal transformation of co-classification networks provides insight on the maturity of a technology. Thus, we developed an approach focusing on the number of edges and isolated subnets in the so-called cumulative co-classification networks. To test the approach, we conducted a case study on the field of additive manufacturing.

Introduction

Besides scientific publications, patents are the main source of data for data-driven foresight activities. One important attribute of patents is the classification in International Patent Classification (IPC) and Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) classes, which are assigned to every patent in the process of application. Those classes provide insight on the content of the patent document, and span technology fields. Since each patent document can be mapped to multiple classes, it stands to reason to analyze the co-classification of those classes. However, the temporal evolution of the corresponding networks is often neglected. This paper aims to explore the development of co-classification networks over time and to evaluate it with respect to the foresight process.

Background

Data Driven Foresight (short DDF) describes the task of analyzing data to gain insight on possible technology developments or, more general, on possible and probable futures (John 2018; Voros 2003). What type of data (source) is used for DDF mainly depends on the question which is to be answered. It is generally assumed, that the technological advancements of tomorrow are developed in the laboratories today. Meaning, that theoretical foundations can, in most cases, be found in scientific publications first. Regarding the actual application of new knowledge or technologies, patent data provides more meaningful insights. Thus, patents can be used to analyze, if a technology is still in the stage of mostly basic research (and thus is not sufficiently represented in patents), or if it is already deemed to be applicable to real-world problems. In other words, patents yield information on the maturity of a technology – if their data is properly analyzed and interpreted.

To do so, either the textual part of a patent can be used, namely title, abstract, claims, or the metadata, such as assignees, citations and dates, can be extracted. One of the most important characteristics are the classification schemes. The most common ones are the IPC, the CPC and the United States Patent Classification (USPC). They consist of a tree structure, organized into sections, classes and groups. The IPC (respectively CPC) consists of 8 (9) sections which are split up into over 70.000 (250.000) subgroups. Since all patents are classified into one or more of those groups upon application, they promise to be a rich source for analysis.

Sasaki et al.; Sasaki and Sakata 2021, for example, used the hierarchical structure to identify and predict technology-spinoffs. In the last years, IPC and CPC classes have often been

included in analyses of the structure of specific technologies, such as nanotechnology, bioenergy, IoT and others (Wang et al. 2018; Tur et al. 2022; Da Bueno et al. 2018; Mazlumi and Agha Mohammadali Kermani 2022; Luis Míguez et al. 2018; Jin et al. 2021; Ji et al. 2020; Tang et al. 2020; Son and Cho 2020). In the research of patent classifications, the focus often lies on the co-occurrence of classes, which are used to build a network and analyse its properties. Those co-occurrence networks, also called co-classification networks or knowledge graphs, are often build on the 3rd or 4th level of the classification scheme (Tang et al. 2020), and clustered with respect to certain properties (Da Bueno et al. 2018). One prominent use case is the identification and inspection of technological convergence (Lv et al. 2018; Wenjing et al. 2021). Wenjing et al. also incorporate another dimension, namely time, by splitting the data into four time periods. In this work of progress, we argue, that the temporal dimension and the evolution of the co-classification network should be further considered for assessing the maturity of technology fields.

Methods

For citation data, Huang et al. (2022) analysed co-citation networks and argue, that the number of isolated sub-networks and the number of edges over time can provide insights into the maturity of a technology. We argue, that similar insights can be gained from the co-classification networks of IPC or CPC classes in a set of patents. In addition, our approach has the advantage, that IPC and CPC classes are mapped to every patent document, while citation and reference data can be sparse.

Figure 1 shows the methodology of the approach. It consists of five steps. First a set of patent documents is retrieved based on a suitable search query. From those documents, the metadata are extracted. Besides the ID, the publication year and the IPC or CPC classification, the type of the document (namely application, publication, grant) is obtained. Therefor it will be possible to compare the results depending on the document type in the end. From the IDs and the classifications, a cumulative co-classification network is created for each year, and from each network indicators (such as the number of edges and isolated subnets) are computed. At last those indicators are plotted and approximated by a model.

Figure 1: Framework for evolving patent co-classification networks

Building cumulative co-classification networks

In a co-classification network, the nodes represent the classification classes, while an edge represents the co-classification of two classes, meaning that there is an edge between class A and class B, if there is a document which is classified to both classes. To analyse the evolution of this network, it is build for every year available in the dataset for all previous years including said year. This approach is chosen, because the co-classifications of each year are passed on to all following years. In other words the cumulative co-classification network $N(y_i)$ for year y_i is a sum of all previous networks y_0 to y_i : $N(y_i) = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} N(y_j) + nodes(y_i) + edges(y_i)$.

Extracting indicators

From each network, the number of edges can be extracted. In this case, the number grows every year, since no edges are removed. Additionally, the number of isolated subnets is determined. A high number of subnets can be interpreted as a high amount of isolated applications or use cases for the technology under investigation. While the number of edges only grows, the number of isolated subnets can also decline, if subnets are connected by new edges to other subnets. If the whole network is connected, there is only one isolated subnet. The choice of using the number of edges and number of isolated subnets out of the plethora of indicators is inspired by the work of Huang et al. (2022).

Interpreting indicators

If the number of edges increases significantly fast, a lot of new ideas are developed and patented, and new connections are formed in the topic. This is especially the case for emerging topics. While a technology matures, the number of new edges starts decreasing, until it stagnates. A rising number of isolated subnets, however, can be interpreted as an increase in new applications or fields of application for a technology. A stagnant number of subnets means no new fields are exploited. A decreasing number of subnets indicates that former isolated subnets are merging into bigger ones, i.e. the topic is consolidating. This can especially be insinuated if the number of edges increases simultaneously. If no new ideas are added to the pool of technology applications, the technology is assumed to have a certain degree of maturity. Thus, the combination of both indicators is expected to provide significant insights on the maturity of a technology.

Findings

To test the approach, a case study for the field of additive manufacturing was conducted. For reasons of comparability, the search query was inspired by the core lexical terms of the search query derived by Huang et al. and the resulting dataset was reduced to documents published before 2016 and patented in the USA. Due the lack of space, the query is not inserted here, but is gladly shared upon request. It does not include classification codes, so as not to influence the analysis by artificially limiting or expanding the set of classification codes in the data. The data is derived from the Patbase dataset, a well-established provider of world-wide patent data. 8.337 documents from 3.600 families were extracted (November 2022).

Figure 2 shows the cumulated CPC subgroup co-classification networks between 1986 and 2015. The CPC was chosen over IPC because it comprises more subgroups, yielding more possibilities for classification and thus creating more detailed networks. On one hand, the number of isolated subnets steadily increases over the years from 28 in 1986 to 128 subnets in 2015. On the other hand, one big subnet develops, which gradually annexes smaller subnets. Thus, the number of edges also increases steadily. **Figure 3** confirms those observations. The graph shows the cumulative number of edges and isolated subnets for each year. The next step at this point would be the curve fitting. Because of a lack of space in this document, this step

will not be addressed further, other than to mention, that work has been done which confirmed that the curve as whole can be fitted best to a logarithmic function.

Furthermore, the curve can be split into 3 parts: the emerging stage, the growth stage and the stagnation stage (Table 1). In the emerging stage, the technology is still new – it is an emerging technology. Over time, inventors from different research fields pick up the technology and incorporate it into their inventions, the technology field is growing. At a later point, the possibilities for the technology to be used in different applications is exhausted, thus, first the number of isolated sub-networks, and then the number of edges, stagnates. At this point, the technology is not emerging anymore, but well-established. Or course this process can also repeat itself.

Figure 2: Cumulated CPC co-classification networks for the years 1986, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015

Figure 3: Cumulated number of isolated subnets and edges for the years 1902-2015

Table 1: Stages of maturity for additive manufacturing, comparison between this approach and the approach by Huang et al. (2022).

Stage	Timeframe	Description	Timeframe from Huang et al.
Emerging stage	1902-1992	The technology is first addressed.	1986-1999
Growth stage	1993-2009	The technology is becoming popular and spread in different fields.	2000-2013
Stagnation stage	2010-2015	The technology is well established in multiple fields, it is „mature“.	2014-2015

Discussion and evaluation

The findings from above support our thesis from the beginning. The approach offers insight into the maturity of additive manufacturing technologies. It is expected, that the number of subnets is not growing significantly after 2015, although more connections are established between the classifications. This fits the fact, that the number of nodes and edges is bounded by the overall number of subgroups in the classification scheme. Interestingly, by comparing the above defined stages with those from Huang et al. (see **Table 1**), it becomes clear, that there is an offset of -7 to -4 years. This could indicate, that the method presented here is able to track – or even forecast – changes in the maturity of a technology at an earlier point than the analysis of co-citations. However, for evaluation, the findings should be compared to other indicators such as the publication dynamic. Additionally, the years after 2015 have to be addressed. Of course, this case study does not verify the general validity of the approach.

Conclusion

The aim of this research currently in progress is to determine, if the evolution of the co-classification of IPC or CPC classes in a set of patents for one technology or topic can help approximating its maturity level. A case study on additive manufacturing was carried out to test the approach explained in the Methods section. The findings support the thesis from the beginning and thus the approach will be further pursued. In the next steps, the data after 2016 will be added, and it will be compared to other indicators in patent analysis, to further evaluate the findings. Additionally, the approach will be used on other topics, to test its universality. Certain parameters, including the choice of CPC over IPC and differences in the analysis of all documents and single types of documents (e.g. applications, grants), will be modified. Furthermore, it would be interesting to test this approach for the evaluation and comparison of actors rather than topics. The goal is to provide foresight researchers, patent analysts and others interested in the data-driven approximation of the maturity of technologies, with meaningful, transparent and easily comparable insights for further analysis.

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